

SROC Serbian Radiation Oncology Congress

Abstract book

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SBRT in prostate cancer

Predrag Petrašinić

Institute for Oncology and Radiology of Serbia

Patients with prostate cancer (PC) which requires treatment can be managed with either radiotherapy (RT) or surgery. RT is well established treatment option for all risk groups, combined with androgen deprivation therapy (ADT) in intermediate and high-risk patients. Dose-escalated RT shows superior treatment outcome over standard dose RT and escalation can be achieved with modern technique external beam RT (EBRT) or with addition of brachytherapy (BT) to EBRT. Since dose-escalation with EBRT requires long overall treatment time, shorter RT schedules were created utilizing hypofractionation. Advances in imaging and RT delivery techniques have allowed treatment of PC patients using ultra-hypofractionated RT called stereotactic body radiation therapy (SBRT). SBRT is defined as “an external beam radiation therapy method used to very precisely deliver a high dose of radiation to an extracranial target within the body, using either a single dose or a small number of fractions”.

Rationale for using SBRT in prostate cancer comes from radiobiology, which is best described by α/β ratio. Current fractionation studies are consistent with conclusion that prostate cancer cells have very low α/β ratio (compared to other tumors), providing the basis for treating PC with high doses per fraction. Today most common SBRT regimes are 35–40 Gy in 5 fractions.

First research results supporting use of SBRT came from moderate hypofractionation trials, and later from phase I and II trials that used SBRT. Nowadays, there are two published randomized trials that supports SBRT treatment for prostate cancer in terms of effectiveness and toxicity compared to standard fractionation high dose regimes. Also, there are more randomized studies still ongoing and we are awaiting results.

During SBRT treatment, a highly conformal dose is delivered to the prostate while sparing the surrounding normal tissue (rectum and bladder), with steep dose fall off. This requires meticulous treatment plan-

ning and radiation delivery, starting with positioning, use of additional imaging for target definition (fusion with magnetic resonance images), strict adherence to dose volume constraints and employment of image guided radiation therapy (IGRT) for inter and intrafraction target tracking.

SBRT is a safe and efficient option for treating patients with PC. Additional research is needed to compare it with other modalities, explore possible modality combinations and employ novel technological approaches to further limit toxicity.

Keywords: SBRT, prostate cancer, imaging

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